

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component HCK Bioinformatics

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Literature research of HCK has been summarized extensively by P.M. Weerawarna et al. in “IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component Evaluation of Literature Compounds as Lyn Chemical Probes” <https://zenodo.org/record/8335611>. In this document, the evidence from BCB core research is summarized below.

HCK (hematopoietic cell kinase) is a proto-oncogene and, like LYN, a Src family tyrosine kinase. The encoded protein is primarily hemopoietic, particularly in cells of the myeloid and B-lymphoid lineages. It helps transmit signals from cell surface receptors and plays an important role in the regulation of innate immune responses, including neutrophil, monocyte, macrophage and mast cell functions, phagocytosis, cell survival and proliferation, cell adhesion and migration. Most importantly, together with PTPN6, LYN, PLCG2, and other nominated drug targets, it is involved in the microglia pathogen phagocytosis pathway, which may contribute to the pathology of AD or the clearance of amyloid plaque. Together with LYN, HCK phosphorylates multiple proteins including immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory/activation motif (ITIM/ITAM) containing protein such as DAP12, mediating the latter signaling downstream of TREM2 receptor activation of microglia (Figure-1). HCK phosphorylates a few other potential AD drug candidates INPP5D, PLCG2, VAV1 and WAS.

Figure-1 LYN/HCK and PTPN6 in the microglia activation.

The same as LYN, HCK was found to be frequently coexpressed with other core microglia genes in the AD only brain transcriptomic cohorts of five datasets [1] and the eight dataset study (Table -1). It is also found in a meta gene coexpression study to be in the coexpression modules of microglia and immune response modules in DLPFC, CBE, STG, FP, IFG, PHG, and TCX regions [2]. It is also a disease-associated human microglia marker gene in the ROSMAP single cell transcriptomic study [3].

AD3_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74
ABI3, ARHGAP30, ARHGDI3, ARPC1B, BTK, C1QA, C1QB, C3, C3AR1, CD300A, CD74, CD86, CSF1R , CSF3R, CTSS, CYBA, CYBB, CYTL1, DOCK2, DOCK8, FCGR2A, FLI1, FPR1, GIMAP4, GIMAP6, GIMAP8, GPSM3, HAVCR2, HCK , HCLS1, HLA-DMB, HLA-DOA, HLA-DRA, IFI30, IL10RA, INPP5D , ITGAM, ITGB2, LAIR1, LCP1, LGALS9, LILRA2, LY86, MFNG, MS4A4A, MS4A6A, MS4A7, MYO1F, NCKAP1L, PIK3AP1, PLCG2 , PLEK, PTPN6 , PTPRC, RHBDF2, RNASE6, SERPINA1, SIPA1, SLA, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, SLC7A7, SLCO2B1, STK10, SYK, TAL1, TBXAS1, TLR2, TLR7, TMEM119, TREM2, TYROBP , VAV1, VSIG4, WAS, WDFY4

Table -1 Microglia core coexpression module AD3 from frequent coexpression network mining on eight large AD patient brain transcriptomic datasets.

HCK is significantly differentially expressed in the bulk tissue transcriptomics of AD vs. normal human brains, as well as in the excitatory neurons of the ROSMAP AD single cell data (Table-2).

Table-2 Differential gene expression of HCK in single cell and bulk tissue.

Gene Symbol	Cell Type/ Study	Data Source	log2_foldchange	adj_p_value	Compare Status
HCK	excitatory neurons	[3]	-0.1157	9.71E-05	pathology vs no-pathology
HCK	excitatory neurons	[3]	0.0349	5.93E-04	early-pathology vs no-pathology
HCK	GSE33000	[1]	0.433	4.18E-23	pathology vs no-pathology
HCK	MSBB	[1]	0.328	6.03E-06	pathology vs no-pathology
HCK	GSE48350	[1]	0.335	3.17E-04	pathology vs no-pathology

HCK interacts with PLCG1 and VAV1 tightly in the protein-protein interaction network analysis. It

directly phosphorylates VAV1, which plays an important role in hematopoiesis, especially in T-cell and B-cell and macrophage development and activation (Figure-2). The activation of macrophage may directly involves HCK phosphorylation of VAV [4]. It also interacts with PLCG1, which is involved in the production of diacylglycerol (DAG) and inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP3).

Figure-2 HCK PPI network from STRING.

The same as LYN, in our recent progressive study shows HCK gene expression is positively associated with disease progression in both male and female cohorts of ROSMAP study.

Unlike many of the proposed AD drug targets, HCK has long been studied as a potential cancer drug target, which have generated multiple inhibitors, antibodies, siRNAs, knockout cell lines and mouse strains to facilitate AD research (please see details in the literature review TEP of LYN/HCK).

Reference:

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2. Wan Y., et al. Meta-Analysis of the Alzheimer's Disease Human Brain Transcriptome and Functional Dissection in Mouse Models. *Cell Rep.* 2020 Jul 14;32(2):107908. doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2020.107908.

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4. English, B. K. et al. Bacterial LPS and IFN- γ trigger the tyrosine phosphorylation of vav in macrophages: evidence for involvement of the hck tyrosine kinase. *J. Leukocyte Biology*, 01 December 1997 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jlb.62.6.859>